

Modeling the retention of rumen boluses for the electronic identification of goats

Journal:	<i>Journal of Dairy Science</i>
Manuscript ID:	JDS-10-3210
Article Type:	Research
Date Submitted by the Author:	26-Feb-2010
Complete List of Authors:	Carné, Sergi; Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Ciència Animal i dels Aliments Caja, Gerardo; Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Ciència Animal i dels Aliments Ghirardi, Juan; Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Ciència Animal i dels Aliments Salama, Ahmed; University Autònoma of Barcelona, Ciència Animal i dels Aliments
Key Words:	electronic identification, goat, rumen bolus, transponder

1 **INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY**

2

3 **Retention of electronic rumen boluses in goats. *Carné et al.***

4 A total of 2,482 rumen boluses were used to construct a regression model of bolus retention in
5 goats, mainly focusing on dairy goats. Bolus retention rate ranged from 0 to 100%, and a

6 logistic regression was established ($R^2 = 0.98$) with bolus weight and volume as covariates.

7 Increase of bolus specific gravity was a key feature to optimize bolus retention rate, and allowed
8 reducing bolus size. Currently available radio translucent and high specific gravity materials are

9 the main limitation to manufacture suitable boluses. Medium-sized boluses (10 to 15 mL) of 58

10 to 73 g are recommended in practice for goats.

11 MODELING ELECTRONIC BOLUS RETENTION IN GOATS

12

13 **Modeling the retention of rumen boluses for the electronic identification of**
14 **goats**

15

16 **S. Carné,* G. Caja, *¹ J. J. Ghirardi*², and A. A. K. Salama*†**

17 *Grup de Recerca en Remugants, Departament de Ciència Animal i dels Aliments,

18 Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain

19 †Sheep and Goat Research Department, Animal Production Research Institute, 12311 Dokki,

20 Giza, Egypt

¹Corresponding author: gerardo.caja@uab.cat.

²Current address: Shearwell Data Ltd., Mariano Acosta 215, 1842 Buenos Aires, Argentina.

21 **ABSTRACT**

22 A regression model of the retention of rumen boluses in the reticulorumen of goats was
23 constructed. With this aim, 2,482 boluses were administered to goats from dairy (Murciano-
24 Granadina, n = 1,326; Alpine, n = 381) and meat (Blanca de Rasquera, n = 532) breeds. A
25 total of 19 bolus types made of different materials (ceramic, plastic tubes filled with concrete
26 and silicone, and ballasts) were used, thereby obtaining a wide variation in bolus features: o.d.
27 (9 to 22 mm), length (37 to 84 mm), weight (5 to 111 g), volume (2.5 to 26 mL), and specific
28 gravity (SG; 1.0 to 5.5). Each bolus contained a half-duplex glass encapsulated transponder
29 (32 × 3.8 mm), and was administered using adapted balling guns. Goats also wore 2 visual
30 plastic ear tags: V1 (double flag, 5.1 g), and V2 (flag-button, 4.2 g). Bolus and ear tag
31 retention (retained/monitored × 100) was recorded for at least 1 yr. Dynamic reading
32 efficiency (dynamic reading/static reading × 100) was also evaluated from a total of 1,496
33 bolus readings. No administration incidents or apparent behaviour and performance
34 alterations were observed for any bolus type. Static reading efficiency of retained boluses was
35 100%, except for the prototypes with metal ballasts, which yielded a 93.3% reading
36 efficiency. Retention of metal-ballasted boluses was confirmed using x-ray equipment.
37 Excluding ballasted boluses, a 99.5% dynamic reading efficiency was obtained. Ear tag losses
38 were 6.5 for V1 and 3.7 % for V2, ranging from 3.2 to 7.8% depending on ear tag type and
39 goat breed. Bolus retention varied (0 to 100%) according to their physical features. Obtained
40 data allowed the fitting of a logistic model of bolus retention rate according to bolus volume
41 and weight ($R^2 = 0.98$); the SG was implicitly considered. Inclusion of literature data was
42 discarded as it caused overestimation of retention values when compared to the original
43 model. Estimated weight and SG to produce mini- (5 mL), medium- (15 mL) and standard-
44 sized (22 mL) boluses for 99.95% retention rate in goats were 42.9, 73.0, and 94.1 g, and
45 8.58, 4.87, and 4.28, respectively. In conclusion, increase of specific gravity was fundamental

46 to optimize bolus retention and reduce bolus size in goats. Mini-boluses are not recommended,
47 as no available radio translucent materials reach the required SG. By contrast, medium-sized
48 boluses (10 to 15 mL; SG 5.9 to 5.2) to be administered at early ages and efficiently retained
49 in adult goats could be produced.

50 **Key words:** electronic identification, goat, rumen bolus, transponder

51

52

INTRODUCTION

53

54 During the last years, a number of passive radiofrequency identification (**RFID**) devices
55 have been tested to electronically identify domestic ruminants, including injectable
56 transponders in different body locations (Fonseca et al., 1994; Lambooj et al., 1999), rumen
57 boluses (Caja et al., 1999; Fallon et al., 2002; JRC, 2003), ear tags (Schuiling et al., 2004;
58 Carné et al., 2009a), and leg bands (Abecia et al., 2009; Carné et al., 2009b, 2010). In the case
59 of rumen boluses, these have proved to be easily administered and show a suitable long-term
60 retention when properly designed and administered in sheep and cattle (Hasker and
61 Basingthwaite, 1996; Teyssier et al., 2003; Ghirardi et al., 2006a,b). In this sense, small-
62 sized boluses (5 to 6.5 mL) have been successfully used to permanently identify lambs at
63 early ages (Garín et al., 2005; Ghirardi et al., 2007).

64 A relationship between physical features of boluses and their retention rate in the
65 reticulorumen has been pointed out by different authors (Ribó et al., 1994; Caja et al., 1999;
66 Fallon, 2001). More recently, the possibility of satisfactorily predicting the retention of
67 boluses according to their physical features in both cattle and sheep has been modeled
68 (Ghirardi et al., 2006a,b).

69 In agreement with provisions of current European regulations on sheep and goat
70 identification and registration (EC 21/2004; EC 1560/2007; EC 933/2008), RFID rumen

71 boluses have been used in Spain since 2006 as the electronic device (Real Decreto 947/2005).
72 Nevertheless, retention rate of boluses in Spanish goat breeds has come to be noticeably lower
73 than in sheep, especially in the case of dairy breeds (JRC, 2003; MAPA, 2007; Carné et al.,
74 2009a). It has been suggested that feed management, as well as goat mature size and breed,
75 affect bolus retention rates (MAPA, 2002; Capote et al., 2005; Carné et al., 2009a,c).

76 The objective of this study was to establish a regression model of the retention of rumen
77 boluses in goats of different purposes (dairy and meat) and breeds, according to bolus
78 physical features. Ultimately, results must enable the design of boluses for different purposes
79 (e.g. electronic identification, monitoring sensors, supplement release) which optimize their
80 retention rate in any goat breed and under different production systems.

81

82 MATERIALS AND METHODS

83

84 Animal care conditions and management practices followed procedures stated by the
85 Ethical Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
86 Barcelona, and the guidelines of the Spanish Committee on Animal Electronic Identification
87 (MAPA, 2007).

88

89 *Animals and Management*

90 A total of 2,239 adult goats from 3 breeds (dairy purpose: Murciano-Granadina, n = 1,326;
91 and French Alpine, n = 381; meat purpose: Blanca de Rasquera, n = 532) were used. The
92 Murciano-Granadina goats belonged to 4 commercial farms (Tona, Barcelona, n = 274; Sant
93 Vicenç de Castellet, Barcelona, n = 291; Juneda, Lleida, n = 410; and Terradelles, Girona, n =
94 239) and 1 experimental farm (SIGCE, Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals,
95 Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Bellaterra, Barcelona, n = 112) in Spain. The Murciano-

96 Granadina goats from the commercial farms were managed under intensive conditions, being
97 kept indoors and fed hay and concentrate. In the case of the SIGCE experimental farm, goats
98 additionally grazed 5 h a day (1000 to 1500 h) on cultivated Italian ryegrass pasture. In all
99 cases, does were milked once daily in the morning (0700 to 1100 h). The Alpine goats
100 belonged to 1 commercial farm (Villarcayo, Burgos, Spain) managed similarly to the
101 Murciano-Granadina commercial farms, although in this case does were milked twice daily
102 (0630 and 1730 h).

103 The Blanca de Rasquera goats, a local Catalan breed highly rustic and intended for meat
104 production (Carné et al., 2007), belonged to 1 commercial farm (Horta de Sant Joan,
105 Tarragona, Spain), and were managed in a semi-extensive production system, grazing 8 h/d
106 (1000 to 1800 h) on Mediterranean forest range lands. Kidding does were supplemented with
107 alfalfa hay and concentrate in the shelters.

108 All goats from the SIGCE experimental farm that died or were culled during the
109 experiment were sent to the Pathology Service of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona for
110 necropsy.

111

112 *Visual Ear Tags*

113 The Murciano-Granadina goats were individually identified with either 2 types of official
114 plastic ear tags: **V1**, double flag type (weight, 5.1 g; flag piece dimensions, 37 × 39 mm;
115 Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain), and **V2**, flag-button type (weight, 4.2 g;
116 flag piece dimensions, 38 × 40 mm; Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain). All goats born after July
117 2005 wore V1 in the right ear, according to currently deployable European regulations in this
118 regard. For goats born before July 2005, V2 were applied in the right ear, in agreement with
119 the former European and Spanish regulations on livestock ID (Directive 92/102/CEE; Real
120 Decreto 205/1996), placing the button piece in the inner face of the ear.

121 The Blanca de Rasquera goats were visually identified with either V1 or V2 official ear tag
122 types in a similar way to that detailed for the Murciano-Granadina goats. The Alpine goats
123 had been brought from different French farms and maintained their official ID consisting of 2
124 official flag-flag yellow plastic ear tags (41× 48 mm; Allflex, Vitré, France), according to
125 current French legislation (Arrêté of 26 June 2006).

126

127 *Rumen Boluses and Administration Procedures*

128 A total of 2,482 boluses, belonging to 19 different prototypes and commercial devices, and
129 varying in their physical features (length, o.d., volume, weight, and specific gravity [SG])
130 were used (Table 1). Administration of boluses with extremely different physical features was
131 expected to result in a wide range of retention rate values, thereby allowing the build up of a
132 regression model of bolus retention in the reticulorumen of goats according to bolus features.

133 Eleven bolus types were cylindrical devices made of non-porous dense ceramic materials,
134 of which 3 were commercial devices for ruminant electronic identification, and the remaining
135 8 were specially made prototypes. Four more boluses consisted of cylindrical plastic tubes
136 containing 1 small sized bolus and different filling materials (silicon, concrete, or metal
137 ballasts). The remaining 4 bolus types consisted of ceramic prototypes with stainless steel
138 ballasts attached to one end in order to increase the SG.

139 A random sample of 10 boluses of each type (n = 190) was collected to measure their
140 physical features under laboratory conditions using a precision weighing scale (accuracy, 0.01
141 g; BP 3100 P, Sartorius AG, Göttingen, Germany) and an electronic digital caliper (accuracy,
142 0.03 mm; Shaodong Feiyue Hardware Tools Factory, Yiwu, China).

143 The SG (density rate of a given substance with respect to density of water at 1 atm of
144 pressure and 4°C) of each bolus was measured according to the Archimedes principle by

145 contrasting the weight of the bolus with the weight of its volume of distilled water, similarly
146 to the method described by Ghirardi et al. (2006a).

147 Each bolus contained a half-duplex glass encapsulated transponder of 32 × 3.8 mm (length
148 × o.d.), which worked at a frequency of 134.2 kHz in agreement with the International
149 Organization for Standardization (ISO) 11785 standard on animal electronic ID (ISO, 1996a).
150 In goats born after July 2005, transponder codes included the country (Spain, 0724), re-
151 tagging counter (00), species (sheep and goat, 04), and a 12-digit serial number in which the
152 autonomous community (Catalonia, 09) was included, according to the current Spanish (Real
153 Decreto 947/2005) and European (EC 21/2004; 2006/968/EC) regulations. For the rest of the
154 goats, ISO transponders with the ICAR (2010) manufacturer codes (Allflex, 982;
155 Innoceramics, 957; Rumitag, 964) and a 12-digit serial number were used, in agreement with
156 ISO 11784 standard (ISO, 2000).

157 All boluses were administered using balling guns adapted to each bolus type.
158 Administration was done as previously described by Caja et al. (1999) and Carné et al.
159 (2009c).

160 To check for possible electronic failures during administration procedures, each bolus was
161 read immediately before and after administration by using full-ISO radio frequency handheld
162 transceivers (Ges2S, Rumitag) able to read boluses at a minimum distance of 20 cm, as
163 specified in the European Regulation in this regard (EC 933/2008). For the post-
164 administration readings, a directional caudo-cranial sweep in the abdomen region was
165 performed with handheld transceivers to ensure the proper descent of the bolus into the
166 reticulorumen. Subsequently, bolus type and goat ID data (goat breed, and ear tag and farm
167 codes) were typed and stored into the reader.

168

169 ***Monitoring of Identification Devices***

170 Boluses were read in static conditions (animals restrained) with the handheld reader at wk
171 1 and mo 1 after administration to register early losses, and thereafter every 2 mo until 12 to
172 18 mo depending on the administration date. From the overall 309 goats that lost the
173 administered bolus prototypes, 243 were reidentified with an improved bolus design. Boluses
174 that could not be monitored for at least 1 yr of study were excluded from calculations as 1 yr
175 is the minimum time frame indicated by the ICAR to carry out extended field tests on the use
176 of livestock ID devices (ICAR, 2007). Additionally, performances of ear tags in Murciano-
177 Granadina (V1, n = 168; V2, n = 502) and Blanca de Rasquera (V1, n = 218; V2, n = 276)
178 goats were registered at 1 yr. Lost ear tag of French Alpine goats were periodically replaced
179 by the owner and no retention rate could be recorded.

180 The retention of ID devices was expressed as:

$$181 \quad \text{Retention rate (\%)} = (\text{no. retained devices} / \text{no. monitored devices}) \times 100$$

182 Unreadable boluses were deemed as lost. Additionally, dynamic reading controls were
183 carried out in 3 farms of Murciano-Granadina goats, as well as in the Alpine and Blanca de
184 Rasquera goat farms. A portable runway (width, 40 cm; length, 200 to 300 cm) with a left-
185 side-installed frame antenna (94 × 52 cm; Rumitag) in vertical position, and connected to a
186 stationary transceiver F-210 (Rumitag) was used. A minimum reading distance in static
187 conditions of 50 cm, as laid down in the European regulation in this regard (EC 933/2008),
188 was checked before goats passed through the runway. A handheld transceiver was used to
189 confirm bolus readability in static conditions (bolus retention) whenever an unread bolus was
190 detected; bolus losses were not included in the dynamic reading efficiency data. Bolus
191 prototypes with metal ballasts were also excluded, as electric conductivity of metal may
192 interfere with radio frequency electromagnetic fields and dramatically reduce the reading
193 distance achieved. The reading efficiency under dynamic conditions was calculated as:

$$194 \quad \text{Dynamic reading efficiency (\%)} = (\text{no. read devices} / \text{no. readable devices}) \times 100$$

195

196 *Statistical Analyses*

197 Bolus retention data were analyzed with a nonlinear least squares regression model, using
198 the NLIN procedure of SAS v.9.1 (SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC) and assuming a logistic
199 distribution, as previously carried out in cattle and sheep (Ghirardi et al., 2006a,b). The final
200 model included the volume (**V**) and weight (**W**) of boluses as independent covariates:

$$201 \qquad \qquad \qquad y = \frac{A}{202 \qquad \qquad \qquad 1 + b_0 \cdot e^{-(b_1 \cdot V + b_2 \cdot W)}} \\ 203 \\ 204$$

205 being: *y*, the bolus retention rate (response variable); *b*₀, *b*₁, and *b*₂, the regression
206 coefficients; and *A*, the maximum value of bolus retention rate expressed as a percentage (*A* =
207 100). The WEIGHT statement of SAS was used to allow for a weighted regression according
208 to the number of boluses of each type evaluated.

209 Retention rate of ear tags was analyzed with the CATMOD procedure of SAS, and a Logit
210 model with an estimation method of maximum likelihood (Cox, 1970) was used. Effects
211 evaluated were breed (Murciano-Granadina and Blanca de Rasquera) and ear tag type (V1 and
212 V2). The CATMOD procedure was also used to analyze the bolus dynamic reading
213 efficiency, evaluating the effects of bolus type, goat breed, and herd.

214 In all cases, significance was declared at *P* < 0.05 and variables that were not significant (*P*
215 > 0.20) were removed from the final models.

216

217 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

218

219 *Features of Boluses, and Administration and Reading Performances*

220 Features of each bolus type are detailed in Table 1. For practical purposes, boluses used in
221 this study were divided into 3 categories according to their volume: small-sized (2.7 to 7.2

222 mL), medium-sized (11.6 to 15.4 mL), and regular or standard-sized boluses (18.1 to 26.0
223 mL). With regard to their dimensions, boluses ranged from 37.4 to 83.8 mm in length, and
224 from 9.3 to 22.1 mm in o.d. Boluses also varied in weight, ranging from 5.3 to 110.8 g, as
225 well as SG, ranging from 1.0 to 5.5. Prototypes with attached stainless steel ballasts were not
226 cylindrical, as the ballast was a ball and had a larger o.d. than the body of the bolus. A total of
227 7 bolus types in our study (#2, 3, 4, 9, 12, 14 and 15; Table 1) have already been tested in
228 fattening lambs and adult sheep (Teyssier et al., 2003; Garín et al., 2005; Ghirardi et al.,
229 2006b, 2007), and in goats (Carné et al., 2009ac).

230 No incidences at bolus administration were reported for any of the bolus types. Moreover,
231 a large bolus prototype (#10, 26 mL), which had never been tested in small ruminants, was
232 easily and safely administered to goats in our experiment. These findings confirm earlier
233 results in sheep and goats where 22-mL boluses were safely administered by trained operators
234 to adult sheep and goats (Caja et al., 1999; Ghirardi et al., 2006a; Carné et al., 2009c) as well
235 as to replacement sheep and goats with BW greater than 30 and 25 kg, respectively (Caja et
236 al., 1999; Carné et al., 2009a). No casualties registered during the study appeared to be related
237 to bolus administration or their long-term location in the reticulorumen; moreover, no
238 necropsy reports of dead goats from the experimental farm indicated any damage caused by
239 the bolus, and in all cases the bolus was properly located in the reticulorumen.

240 Retained boluses could be easily read in static conditions in the shelters and the milking
241 parlor by using handheld readers (static reading efficiency, 100%), except for the prototypes
242 with metal ballasts (static reading efficiency, 93.3%). In these last cases, several reading
243 attempts were frequently necessary probably due to interferences in the signal emitted by the
244 transponder. In fact, proper retention of 8 of these ballasted boluses had to be confirmed at the
245 end of the study by using portable X-ray equipment (Model X803G, MinXray Inc.,
246 Northbrook, IL, USA).

247 Fallon (2001) described large RFID boluses made of plastic with steel ballasts attached to
248 one end; these ballasts increased the SG and allowed a swift submersion through the rumen
249 content. Nevertheless, the body of the bolus encased larger transponders to compensate for
250 poor reading performance due to interferences caused by the metal ballast. The use of this sort
251 of device, with SG up to 2.75, has been described in sheep (Caja et al., 1996) and cattle
252 (Lambooij et al., 1999; Fallon et al., 2002).

253 With respect to dynamic reading efficiency, boluses with attached metal ballasts were not
254 taken into account as unsuitable reading performance was anticipated. A total of 1,496 bolus
255 readings were carried out, with the goats passing in front of the frame antenna at a speed of up
256 to 2 goats/s. At the end of the study, 8 reading failures were registered, thereby obtaining a
257 reading efficiency under dynamic conditions of 99.5%. Moreover, no differences according to
258 bolus type, goat breed or herd could be established. Carné et al. (2010) reported bolus
259 dynamic reading efficiency of 95.2% in the same goat breed, using similar HDX transponders
260 and a lateral antenna, but under electronic collision environment. Readabilities greater than
261 99.5% were described by using both mini- (3 to 5 mL) and standard-sized (22 mL) boluses in
262 different meat and dairy sheep breeds (Ghirardi et al., 2006b); no bolus or herd effect were
263 detected in this case. Moreover, Stewart et al. (2007) and Wallace et al. (2007) showed 93.8
264 to 99.9% dynamic reading efficiency of electronic ear tags, according to RFID technology
265 and transceiver type used in cattle.

266

267 ***Bolus Retention and Regression Model***

268 Retention of the different bolus types is shown in Table 1. Retention rates ranged from 0 to
269 100% ($P < 0.001$) as anticipated according to the variety of bolus features, and previous
270 research in sheep and cattle (Ghirardi et al., 2006a,b). The lowest retention rates (< 3.8%)
271 were obtained for the bolus types #1, 5 and 8, which varied in weight (5.3 to 46.2 g) and

272 volume (5.2 to 22.2 mL), showing $SG < 2.2$. On the contrary, the greatest retention rate values
 273 (100%) were observed with bolus types #6, 10, 18 and 19, which corresponded to a wide
 274 range of weights (35.5 to 110.8 g) and volumes (7.2 to 26.0 mL), although in these cases SG
 275 > 4.1 . Thus, SG appeared to be of major relevance for bolus performance according to
 276 retention results. Only the 4 bolus types where no losses occurred were above the ICAR
 277 retention requirement for animal ID ($> 98\%$ at 1 yr after administration; ICAR, 2007).

278 At the end of the study, 2,299 boluses (92.6%) had been monitored for at least 1 yr, which
 279 corresponded to 1,398 (60.8%) Murciano-Granadina, 394 (17.1%) Alpine and 507 (22.1%)
 280 Blanca de Rasquera goats; these boluses made up the dataset utilized to assess the regression
 281 model.

282 Different parameters (weight, volume, SG , length, and o.d.) were evaluated to properly
 283 estimate bolus retention rate according to their physical features. Results obtained proved that
 284 a logistic model taking the weight and volume of boluses as covariates offered the greatest
 285 adjustment ($R^2 = 0.98$; $P < 0.001$), as similarly indicated previously by using analogous
 286 models for sheep and beef cattle (Ghirardi et al., 2006a,b). It bears mentioning that when
 287 considering weight and volume, SG was implicitly considered as well. The equation of the
 288 model estimating the percentage of retention rate in goats according to bolus weight and
 289 volume was as follows:

$$290 \quad \text{Retention rate (\%)} = \frac{100}{291 \quad 1 + 0.734 \cdot e^{0.788 \cdot V - 0.262 \cdot W}} \quad (1)$$

292
293

294 Factual retention data and estimated retention curves according to the different bolus
 295 volumes are shown in Figure 1. For any given bolus volume, retention rate increased when
 296 weight and SG increased. In contrast, increasing the bolus weight while maintaining the SG
 297 invariable, only offered a moderate improvement of the retention rate. It was also confirmed
 298 that suitable retention of small boluses is feasible if appropriately designed. As previously

299 indicated in sheep and cattle, a reduction in bolus volume not affecting the retention
300 performance can be accomplished by increasing the SG (Garín et al., 2005; Ghirardi et al.,
301 2006a,b).

302 Error of the estimated retention averaged 2.4 units of percentage (Figure 2), being greater
303 than those reported in sheep (1.3) and cattle (1.5) by Ghirardi et al. (2006a,b). Greater error in
304 our study may be explained by the larger number of boluses tested and the lower bolus types
305 with 100% retention rate with respect to the aforementioned works. In addition, and unlike
306 other goat breeds, some Spanish dairy breeds have shown a great variability in bolus retention
307 rates (MAPA, 2002, 2007; Carné et al., 2009a). In fact, it has been suggested that breed and
308 management conditions (i.e. feeding conditions) may affect bolus retention in goats (JRC,
309 2003; Capote et al., 2005; Carné et al., 2009a,c).

310 Taking into account this variability, the construction of the model was aimed at obtaining
311 devices with optimum retention rates irrespective of breed and management, rather than
312 estimating the most representative mean retention in the goat species. For this reason, more
313 than 60% of boluses included in the model belonged to Murciano-Granadina Spanish dairy
314 goat, which has been indicated to show the widest range of retention values, generally being
315 poorer than in other breeds evaluated (MAPA, 2002, 2007; Capote et al., 2005; Pinna et al.,
316 2006). Concentrate-based and small particle sized total mixed rations commonly used in
317 Murciano-Granadina goats have been suggested to affect bolus retention (Carné et al., 2009a).

318 In a subsequent step of our study, available literature referred to the medium and long-term
319 (> 8 mo) bolus retention in goats was joined to the model (Caja et al., 1999; JRC, 2003;
320 Capote et al., 2005; San Miguel et al., 2005; Pinna et al., 2006; MAPA, 2007; Carné et al.,
321 2009a,b) as previously done by Ghirardi et al (2006b) in sheep. The regression coefficients
322 obtained in our meta-analysis were: $b_0 = 0.832$, $b_1 = 0.255$, and $b_2 = -0.715$. Results with our
323 observed data tended to be more conservative than those obtained in the meta-analysis, that is,

324 estimation curves with our data were displaced to the right, thereby indicating that greater
325 weight and specific gravity are required to reach the desired bolus retention. Hereinafter, to
326 facilitate the presentation of results and their subsequent discussion, reference will be made to
327 the volumes of 5, 15 and 22 mL, which were chosen as representative of commercially
328 available mini-, medium-, and standard-sized boluses, respectively. In this sense, differences
329 between the produced model and the meta-analysis were greater when dealing with large
330 bolus volumes. Thus, average differences of estimated retentions including (meta-analysis) or
331 not including (our data) the literature references were 1.7, 4.3 and 6.3% for 5, 15 and 22 mL
332 volumes, respectively. Nevertheless, when focusing on the critical retention > 98% indicated
333 by the ICAR (2007), these differences were reduced to 0, 0.3 and 0.6% for the same volumes
334 considered. In view of the low variability between the 2 models for retention rates close to
335 100%, and the more strict requirements of our data to design boluses with optimum retention,
336 it was concluded that the model obtained with our observed data was more suitable for the
337 purpose of this work.

338 In the present study, taking into consideration the unfavorable scenario of bolus losses
339 previously reported in goats, we decided to evaluate results for a retention rate of 99.95%,
340 thereby being even more stringent with bolus requirements. Hence, the previous equation (1)
341 was rearranged and 2 new equations were obtained, which allowed the assessment of the
342 estimated weight, volume and SG of boluses for their optimum retention in goats:

$$343 \quad W = 27.83 + 3.01 \cdot V \quad (2)$$

$$344 \quad SG = 27.83 / V + 3.01 \quad (3)$$

345 According to these equations, the minimum weight and SG to obtain the desired retention
346 of small (5 mL), medium (15 mL), and standard size (22 mL) boluses were: 42.9 g (SG =
347 8.58), 73.0 g (SG = 4.87) and 94.1 g (SG = 4.28), respectively. Before comparing our results
348 with those obtained in the sheep and beef cattle models (Ghirardi et al., 2006a,b), it should be

349 pointed out that volume and weight coefficients in the published equation of the sheep model
350 (Ghirardi et al., 2006b) were interchanged. Reviewed exponent in the equation of the
351 Ghirardi's sheep model is $0.763 \cdot V - 0.504 \cdot W$, from which we calculated (99.95% retention
352 rate) that $W = 15.34 + 1.51 \cdot V$.

353 For an estimated retention rate of 99.95%, the minimum bolus weights and SG in sheep
354 were: 22.9 g (SG 4.57) for 5-mL boluses, 38.0 g (SG 2.53) for 15-mL boluses, and 48.6 g (SG
355 2.20) for 22-mL boluses. In the case of cattle, estimated weight and SG for the same ration
356 rate and volumes derived from the model of Ghirardi et al. (2006a) were 58.1 g (SG 11.6),
357 74.8 g (SG 4.99), and 86.5 g (SG 3.93), respectively. It is remarkable that values in goats
358 approximately doubled those in sheep, which makes evident the differences between species
359 regarding the retention performance of boluses. On the contrary, differences between goats
360 and cattle were much lesser, although they varied considerably depending on the dimensions
361 of the bolus. No studies referred to interspecies differences in the regurgitation of foreign
362 bodies located in the reticulorumen have been published, which is a key point for the retention
363 of monitoring sensors (e.g. temperature, pH) and slow-release devices (e.g. supplements,
364 antihelminthic, anti-foaming agents).

365 Figure 3 summarizes the results obtained in our study, showing the variety of combinations
366 of weight, volume and SG that would allow producing boluses with an optimum retention rate
367 (99.95%) in goats. From a view of designing boluses for an optimum retention and also of
368 allowing the administration at early ages, the use of high dense boluses with reduced volume
369 is required, agreeing Caja et al. (1999), Fallon (2001) and Ghirardi et al., 2006a,b). As radio
370 frequency translucent materials are necessary for RFID, dense ceramic materials are being
371 used at present for this purpose, and boluses with SG up to 4.1 have been produced. Yet,
372 estimated SG for mini-boluses (e.g. 5 mL of volume) to be retained in goats is greater than
373 8.5. Therefore, as long as currently utilized materials do not allow such high SG values to be

374 reached, the use of mini-boluses for goat ID should be discarded. Unsuitability of mini-
375 boluses for goat ID has already been pointed out in earlier reports (Carné et al., 2009a,c); this
376 is a major difference between sheep and goats as mini-boluses with SG greater than 3.5, and
377 more than 15 g of weight, have been successfully used (retention > 98%) for permanent sheep
378 ID (Teyssier et al., 2003; Ghirardi et al., 2006b, 2007; MAPA, 2007).

379 Results of the present work indicated the need for a SG between 4.9 and 5.8 to produce
380 medium sized boluses (e.g. 10 to 15 mL of volume) which can be properly retained in goats;
381 available radio translucent materials could be successfully used nowadays to obtain boluses
382 with such required physical features.

383

384 ***Ear Tag Retention***

385 Performance of visual ear tags is shown in Table 2. Damages by biting and breakage of the
386 flag pieces were greater ($P < 0.05$) in V2 than in V1 ear tags, and a breed effect was also
387 observed in V2. Most damages registered in this last ear tag type were due to the breakage of
388 the flag piece, thus resulting in button-like ear tags; the breakage of flag pieces in V2 seemed
389 to be caused by a too weak insertion of the flag piece to the ear tag body. As only lost devices
390 were replaced by the veterinary officials during the annual blood sampling campaigns (Carné
391 et al., 2010), yearly incidence of such breakages was not established. These findings may be
392 of relevance for V2 retention as button-button RFID ear tags have been indicated to offer
393 greater long-term retention rates than flag types (Carné et al., 2009a). Retention rate varied
394 among herds (92.2 to 98.0%), although only a tendency of difference ($P = 0.08$) was detected
395 for the V2. Retention of V2 was numerically greater than V1 in the 2 goat breeds evaluated,
396 although only the retention of V1 in Blanca de Rasquera and V2 in Murciano-Granadina goats
397 differed (92.2 vs. 96.8%, respectively; $P < 0.05$). Despite the fact that literature in this regard
398 is limited, losses in our study remained within the wide range of 1.4 to 17.1% reported in

399 different goat breeds (Carné et al., 2009a,b). Yet, visual plastic ear tag retention values in our
400 results did not meet the ICAR recommendations (> 98%) for official animal ID (ICAR, 2007).

401

402

CONCLUSIONS

403

404 Features of boluses affect their retention in the reticulorumen of goats. Moreover, goat
405 boluses need to be heavier and with greater SG than in sheep and cattle. Mini-boluses similar
406 to those used in sheep are not recommended in goats. On the other hand, medium size boluses
407 (10 to 15 mL) with SG of 4.9 to 5.8 could be successfully produced with radio translucent
408 materials for their efficient retention in the reticulorumen of goats, thereby giving response to
409 the current problem of using proper boluses for goat identification.

410

411

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

412

413 This work is part of a research project funded by the Spanish Ministry of Education (Plan
414 Nacional I+D+i; Project AGL-2007-64541). The authors are grateful to the goatherds
415 Salvador and Pepito Miralles (Horta de Sant Joan, Tarragona), José-Luís Casanueva (Sant
416 Vicenç de Castellet, Barcelona), Llorenç and Martí Huguet (Terradelles, Girona), Gerard
417 Porta (Juneda, Lleida), Lluís Mauri (Tona, Barcelona), and Alfonso Andújar and Victor
418 Maeso (Villarcayo, Burgos) for taking part in this Spanish project; to Ramon Costa and the
419 team of the Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals of the Universitat Autònoma de
420 Barcelona (Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain) for the technical assistance and care of the animals;
421 to Joan F. Vilaseca (Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain) for supplying part of
422 the boluses; and to Nic Aldam (Barcelona, Spain) for the English revision of the manuscript.

423

REFERENCES

- 424
425
- 426 Abecia, J. A., and J. Torras. 2009. Aplicación de la pulsera electrónica Patuflex:
427 Identificación de corderas y cabritas de reposición. *Albóitar* 129:54-55.
- 428 Caja, G., F. Barillet, R. Nehring, C. Marie, O. Ribó, E. Ricard, G. Lagriffoul, C. Conill, M. R.
429 Aurel, and M. Jacquin. 1996. Comparison of different devices for electronic identification
430 in dairy sheep. Pages 349–353 in *Performance Recording of Animals*. J. Renaud and J.
431 van Gelder, ed. EAAP Publication No. 87. Wageningen Pers, Wageningen, The
432 Netherlands.
- 433 Caja, G., C. Conill, R. Nehring, and O. Ribó. 1999. Development of a ceramic bolus for the
434 permanent electronic identification of sheep, goat and cattle. *Comp. Elec. Agric.* 24:45-
435 63.
- 436 Capote, J., D. Martín, N. Castro, E. Muñoz, J. Lozano, S. Carné, J. J. Ghirardi, and G. Caja.
437 2005. Retención de bolos ruminales para identificación electrónica en distintas razas de
438 cabras españolas. *ITEA Prod. Animal* 26(Vol. extra):297-299.
- 439 Carné, S., G. Caja, A. A. K. Salama, and J. J. Ghirardi. 2009a. Long-term performance of
440 visual and electronic identification devices in dairy goats. *J. Dairy Sci.* 92:1500-1511.
- 441 Carné, S., G. Caja, M. A. Rojas-Olivares, and A. A. K. Salama. 2009b. Leg bands and rumen
442 boluses for the long-term electronic identification of goats. *J. Anim. Sci.* 87, E-Suppl.
443 2:310 (Abstr.).
- 444 Carné, S., G. Caja, M. A. Rojas-Olivares, and A. A. K. Salama. 2010. Readability of visual
445 and electronic leg tags versus rumen boluses and electronic ear tags for the permanent
446 identification of dairy goats (submitted) Feb. 19, 2010.

- 447 Carné, S., T. A. Gipson, M. Rovai, R. C. Merkel, and G. Caja. 2009c. Extended field test on
448 the use of visual ear tags and electronic boluses for the identification of different goat
449 breeds in the United States. *J. Anim. Sci.* 87:2419-2427.
- 450 Carné, S., N. Roig, and J. Jordana. 2007. La Cabra Blanca de Rasquera: Caracterización
451 estructural de las explotaciones. *Arch. Zootec.* 56:43-54.
- 452 Cox, D. R. 1970. *The Analysis of Binary Data*. Chapman & Hall, London, United Kingdom.
- 453 Fallon, R. J. 2001. The development and use of electronic ruminal boluses as a vehicle for
454 bovine identification. *Rev. sci. tech. Off. int. Epiz.* 20:480-490.
- 455 Fallon, R. J., P. A. M. Rogers, and B. Earley. 2002. Project Report ARMIS No. 4623.
456 Electronic Animal Identification. Beef Production Series No. 46, Grange Research
457 Centre, Dunsany Co, Meath.
- 458 Fonseca, P. D., C. R. Roquete, J. L. Castro, A. G. Condeço, and J. V. Fernandes. 1994.
459 Evaluation of migration, losses and breakages on electronic identification transponders
460 implanted in four different sites in adult goats. In: *Electronic identification of farm*
461 *animals using implantable transponders*. European Union General Directorate VI-
462 FEOGA, European Commission, Brussels. Research Project, Final Report, Vol. II, Exp.
463 UE-03/2.2.
- 464 Garín, D., G. Caja, and C. Conill. 2005. Performance and effects of small ruminal boluses for
465 electronic identification of young lambs. *Livest. Prod. Sci.* 92:47-58.
- 466 Ghirardi, J. J., G. Caja, D. Garín, J. Casellas, and M. Hernández-Jover. 2006a. Evaluation of
467 the retention of electronic identification boluses in the forestomachs of cattle. *J. Anim.*
468 *Sci.* 84:2260-2268.
- 469 Ghirardi, J. J., G. Caja, D. Garín, M. Hernández-Jover, O. Ribó, and J. Casellas. 2006b.
470 Retention of different sizes of electronic identification boluses in the forestomachs of
471 sheep. *J. Anim. Sci.* 84:2865-2872.

- 472 Ghirardi, J. J., G. Caja, C. Flores, D. Garín, M. Hernández-Jover, and F. Bocquier. 2007.
473 Suitability of electronic mini-boluses for the early identification of lambs. *J. Anim. Sci.*
474 85:248-257.
- 475 Hasker, P. J. S., and J. Bassingthwaite. 1996. Evaluation of electronic identification
476 transponders implanted in the rumen of cattle. *Aust. J. Exp. Agric.* 36:19-22.
- 477 ICAR (International Committee for Animal Recording). 2007. International Agreement of
478 Recording Practices. Guidelines approved by the General Assembly held in Kuopio,
479 Finland, June 2006, International Committee for Animal Recording. Rome, Italy.
- 480 ICAR (International Committee for Animal Recording). 2010. Animal Identification: List of
481 manufacturer codes. Available: http://www.icar.org/manufacturer_codes.htm. Accessed
482 Dec. 20, 2009.
- 483 ISO (International Organization for Standardization). 1996a. Agricultural Equipment. Radio-
484 frequency Identification of Animals-Technical Concept. ISO 11785:1996 (E). First
485 edition. Geneva, Switzerland.
- 486 ISO (International Organization for Standardization). 1996b. Agricultural Equipment. Radio-
487 frequency Identification of Animals-Code structure. ISO 11784:1996 (E). Second edition.
488 Geneva, Switzerland.
- 489 JRC (Joint Research Center). 2003. IDEA Project, large scale project on livestock electronic
490 identification. Final Report. v. 5.2. Available: [http://idea.jrc.it/pages%20idea/
491 final%20report.htm](http://idea.jrc.it/pages%20idea/final%20report.htm) Accessed Dec. 15, 2009.
- 492 MAPA (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación). 2002. Informe final del Proyecto
493 IDEA España (1998-2001). Anexo II: Informe técnico sobre pérdidas en ganado caprino.
494 [http://ie.mapya.es/Experiencias/ANEXO-II%20Informe%20Perdidas%20en%20
495 Cabra.pdf](http://ie.mapya.es/Experiencias/ANEXO-II%20Informe%20Perdidas%20en%20Cabra.pdf) Accessed Dec. 20, 2009.

- 496 MAPA (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación). 2007. Identificación Electrónica
497 Animal: Experiencias del MAPA. MAPA, Madrid, Spain.
- 498 Lambooij, E., C. E. Van't Klooster, W. Rossing, A. C. Smits, and C. Pieterse. 1999.
499 Electronic identification with passive transponders in veal calves. *Comp. Elec. Agric.*
500 24:81-90.
- 501 Pinna, W., P. Sedda, G. Moniello, and O. Ribó. 2006. Electronic identification of Sarda goats
502 under extensive conditions in the island of Sardinia. *Small Rum. Res.* 66:286-290.
- 503 Ribó, O., G. Caja, and R. Nehring. 1994. A note on electronic identification using
504 transponders placed in permanent ruminal bolus in sheep and goats. In: *Electronic*
505 *identification of farm animals using implantable transponders.* European Union General
506 Directorate VI-FEOGA, European Commission, Brussels. Research Project, Final Report,
507 Vol. I, Exp. UAB-01/2.6.
- 508 San Miguel, O., G. Caja, R. Nehring, F. Miranda, J. A. Merino, V. Almansa, and M. J. Lueso.
509 2005. Results of the IDEA project on cattle, sheep and goats in Spain. Pages 357-359 in
510 *Performance Recording of Farm Animals State of the Art, 2004.* ed. M. Guellouz, A.
511 Dimitriadou and C. Mosconi. EAAP Publication No 113. Wageningen Academic
512 Publishers, Wageningen, The Netherlands.
- 513 Schuiling, H.J., J. Verkaik, G. Binnendijk, P. Hogewerf, D. Smits, and B. van der Fels. 2004.
514 Elektronische oormerken voor I&R bij schapen en geiten. *PraktijkRapport Schapen 02.*
- 515 Stewart, S. C., P. Rapnicki, J. R. Lewis, and M. Perala. 2007. Detection of low frequency
516 external electronic identification devices using commercial panel readers. *J. Dairy Sci.* 90:
517 4478-4482.
- 518 Teyssier, L., J. L. Gaubert, P. M. Bouquet, C. Maton, and F. Bocquier. 2003. Utilisation de
519 petits bolus pour l'identification électronique des ovins: évaluation du taux de rétention et
520 des effets de changements de mode de conduite. *Renc. Rech. Ruminants* 10:117.

521 Wallace, L. E., J. A. Paterson, R. Clark, M. Harbac, and A. Kellom. 2008. Readability of
522 thirteen different radio frequency identification ear tags by three different multi-panel
523 reader systems for use in beef cattle. *Professional Animal Scientist* 24:384–391.

For Peer Review

524

525 **Table 1.** Features and retention rates of electronic rumen boluses for the permanent identification of goats

Serial number	Bolus type	Bolus features ¹				Goats, No.				Retention rate, %
		length × o.d., mm	Weigh, g	Volume, mL	Specific gravity	Applied	Not recorded ¹⁰	Lost	Retained	
#1	Plastic tube ²	48.1 × 12.1	5.32 ± 0.16	5.15 ± 0.14	1.03 ± 0.02	25	0	25	0	0
#2	Ceramic ³	37.4 × 9.3	9.00 ± 0.04	2.65 ± 0.01	3.40 ± 0.01	45	10	14	21	60.0
#3	Ceramic ³	51.0 × 10.5	13.66 ± 0.03	3.91 ± 0.01	3.49 ± 0.01	92	1	26	65	71.4
#4	Ceramic ³	56.4 × 11.2	20.14 ± 0.21	5.16 ± 0.01	3.90 ± 0.01	636	51	109	476	81.4
#5	Plastic tube ⁴	76.4 × 20.2	35.38 ± 0.21	21.88 ± 0.13	1.62 ± 0.01	30	1	29	0	0
#6	Ceramic + ballast ⁵	72.7 × 15.1	35.45 ± 0.08	7.20 ± 0.04	4.92 ± 0.03	33	3	0	30	100
#7	Ceramic ³	64.1 × 15.5	42.10 ± 0.14	11.63 ± 0.08	3.62 ± 0.01	42	3	3	36	92.3
#8	Plastic tube ⁴	76.6 × 20.2	46.21 ± 0.27	22.23 ± 0.11	2.08 ± 0.01	28	1	26	1	3.7
#9	Ceramic ⁶	67.7 × 16.9	51.56 ± 0.09	14.37 ± 0.03	3.59 ± 0.01	56	8	4	44	91.7
#10	Ceramic + ballast ⁵	79.1 × 19.9	52.92 ± 0.09	9.67 ± 0.06	5.47 ± 0.03	31	2	0	29	100
#11	Plastic tube ⁴	83.8 × 15.3	53.75 ± 0.54	15.41 ± 0.13	3.49 ± 0.04	24	2	1	21	95.5
#12	Ceramic ⁷	62.3 × 19.8	64.87 ± 0.21	18.11 ± 0.06	3.58 ± 0.01	50	5	2	43	95.6
#13	Ceramic ³	76.9 × 18.1	72.53 ± 0.20	18.92 ± 0.12	3.86 ± 0.01	258	19	14	225	94.1
#14	Ceramic ⁸	68.2 × 21.0	75.04 ± 0.29	22.34 ± 0.07	3.36 ± 0.01	504	45	35	424	92.3
#15	Ceramic ³	67.2 × 20.1	80.65 ± 0.23	19.85 ± 0.03	4.06 ± 0.01	150	13	6	131	95.6
#16	Ceramic ³	69.1 × 21.2	82.13 ± 0.48	22.64 ± 0.08	3.63 ± 0.01	393	15	14	364	96.3
#17	Ceramic ³	69.4 × 21.3	84.01 ± 0.09	22.46 ± 0.01	3.74 ± 0.02	30	2	1	27	96.4
#18	Ceramic + ballast ⁹	73.8 × 20.9	97.93 ± 0.13	23.37 ± 0.05	4.19 ± 0.01	30	1	0	29	100
#19	Ceramic + ballast ⁹	79.3 × 22.1	110.81 ± 0.16	26.01 ± 0.05	4.26 ± 0.01	25	1	0	24	100
—	Total, No.	—	—	—	—	2,482	183	309	1,990	—

526 ¹Each bolus contained a glass encapsulated half-duplex transponder (32 × 3.8 mm).527 ²Hand made prototype consisting of a plastic tube filled with silicone and sealed with epoxy resin.528 ³Specially made prototype.529 ⁴Hand made prototype consisting of a plastic tube containing a type 4 ceramic bolus, filled with silicone (type 5) or concrete (type 8) and sealed with epoxy resin.530 ⁵Hand made prototype consisting of a type 4 ceramic bolus with a stainless steel ballast (type 6: 16.7 g; type 10: 32.8 g) attached.

531 ⁶Standard commercial bolus (Innoceramics, Teramo, Italy).

532 ⁷Standard commercial bolus (Allflex, Vitré, France).

533 ⁸Standard commercial bolus (Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Spain).

534 ⁹Hand made prototype consisting of a type 15 bolus with a stainless steel ballast (30.5 g) attached, and a thermo-retractile plastic cover.

535 ¹⁰Animals which died or left the study before 1 yr after bolusing.

536

537

538

539

540

541

542

543

544

545

546

547

548

549

550

For Peer Review

551 **Table 2.** Performance of visual plastic ear tags in Murciano-Granadina (dairy) and Blanca de
 552 Rasquera (meat) goat breeds at 1 yr of study¹

Item	Murciano-Granadina		Blanca de Rasquera		Overall	
	V1	V2	V1	V2	V1	V2
Ear tags, No.	168	502	218	276	386	778
Damaged ² , %	3.0 ^a	13.7 ^b	4.1 ^a	21.7 ^{cx}	3.6 ^a	16.6 ^{bcy}
Lost, %	4.8	3.2	7.8	4.7	6.5	3.7
Retention rate, %	95.2 ^{ab}	96.8 ^b	92.2 ^a	95.3 ^{ab}	93.5 ^a	96.3 ^b

553 ^{a,b}Within a row, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

554 ^{x,y}Within a row, values with different superscripts tended to differ ($P < 0.1$).

555 ¹Abbreviations: V1, double flag type, 5.1 g, 37 × 39 mm flag dimensions (Rumitag,
 556 Esplugues de Llobregat, Spain); V2, flag-button type, 4.2 g, 38 × 40 mm flag dimensions with
 557 the button piece placed on the inner side of the ear (Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain).

558 ²Ear tags with apparent signs of damage caused by biting or breakage of the flag pieces but
 559 still readable.

560 **Figure 1.** Bolus retention rates (%) according to their weight (W, g) and volume (V, mL) in
 561 goats under on-farm conditions (●, small size boluses: 2.7 to 7.2 mL; ○, medium size boluses:
 562 11.6 to 15.4 mL; ◆, standard and large size boluses: 18.1 to 26.0 mL). Lines are the estimated
 563 retention rates for different bolus volumes according to the logistic regression as follows:

$$564 \text{ Retention rate (\%)} = \frac{100}{565 1 + 0.734 \cdot e^{0.788 \cdot V - 0.262 \cdot W}} \\ 566 \\ 567$$

568
 569 **Figure 2.** Comparison of observed and estimated values of bolus retention rate in goats (SEM
 570 = 2.4)

571
 572 **Figure 3.** Bolus weight and volume combinations that allow a retention rate (RR) greater than
 573 99.95% (grey zone) according to bolus specific gravity (SG) in goats on farm conditions.

574 **Figure 1.**

575

576

577

578

579

580

581

582

583

584

585

586

587

588

589 **Figure 2.**

590

Review

591 **Figure 3.**

592

Review